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A Study of Ibn Kathir's Exegesis of Surah Luqman (Verses 13–19): Character Education through the Approach of Tawhid and 'Ubudiyyah.

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Abstract

This study examines the values of character education in Ibn Kathir's Tafsir of Surah Luqman (13–19) using tawhid and 'ubudiyyah as the foundational approaches to Islamic character formation. This qualitative library research applies content analysis to Tafsir al-Qur'an al-'Azim by Ibn Kathir as the primary source. The findings reveal that tawhid nurtures spiritual awareness, honesty, and responsibility, while 'ubudiyyah cultivates discipline, patience, and humility in social life. Both approaches complement one another in shaping a faithful and virtuous Muslim character. Thus, character education grounded in tawhid and 'ubudiyyah remains highly relevant in modern Islamic education to foster morally upright and spiritually conscious individuals.

Keywords: Ibn Kathir's Tafsir, Surah Luqman, character education, tawhid, 'ubudiyyah

Abstrak

Penelitian ini mengkaji nilai-nilai pendidikan karakter dalam *Tafsir Ibn Katsir* terhadap Surah Luqman ayat 13–19 dengan menggunakan pendekatan *tauhid* dan *'ubudiyyah* sebagai dasar pembentukan karakter Islami. Metode penelitian yang digunakan bersifat kualitatif dengan jenis studi kepustakaan melalui analisis isi terhadap teks *Tafsir al-Qur'an al-'Azim* karya Ibn Katsir. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa nilai *tauhid* menumbuhkan kesadaran spiritual, kejujuran, dan tanggung jawab, sedangkan nilai *'ubudiyyah* membentuk kedisiplinan, kesabaran, dan kerendahan hati dalam kehidupan sosial. Kedua pendekatan ini saling melengkapi dalam membentuk karakter Muslim yang beriman dan berakhlak mulia. Oleh karena itu, pendidikan karakter berbasis *tauhid* dan *'ubudiyyah* sangat relevan diterapkan dalam konteks pendidikan Islam modern untuk menumbuhkan pribadi yang beriman, berilmu, dan berkeadaban.

Kata Kunci: *Tafsir Ibn Katsir, Surah Luqman, pendidikan karakter, tauhid, 'ubudiyyah*

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INTRODUCTION

The progress of a nation is inseparable from the quality of its younger generation. Education serves as a fundamental pillar in developing children's character and intellect, both intellectually and morally. However, many educational institutions place greater emphasis on academic achievement rather than moral formation, even though a person's future is strongly shaped by the moral values and character instilled from an early age. Indonesia, in particular, is known for its steadfast adherence to religious principles and ethical values. The nation is also recognized for its culture of hospitality, politeness, and devotion, as well as its long-standing traditions of mutual cooperation (*gotong royong*) and deliberation (*musyawarah*) in facing social challenges.¹

The phenomenon of moral decline and the character crisis among today's younger generation has become a major challenge in the field of education. The rise of social deviance such as bullying, a lack of respect toward parents and teachers, consumerist behavior, and the misuse of digital technology indicates that the current character education efforts have not been fully effective in shaping individuals with noble character. Although the Indonesian government has implemented character education within the national curriculum, its application still tends to focus primarily on cognitive and social-behavioral

¹ Mafaza Amrillah and Ainun Nadlif, "Pendidikan Karakter Anak Usia Dini pada Surah Luqman Ayat 12–19 Berdasarkan *Tafsir Ibn Kathir*," *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi* 23, no. 3 (October 2023): 2570, <https://doi.org/10.33087/jiubj.v23i3.4222>

aspects, while the spiritual and theological (tawhid) dimensions are often overlooked. In fact, true character education must touch the deepest aspects of the human being, namely the awareness of one's identity as a creation of God who bears moral and spiritual responsibility.²

In Islamic thought, character education cannot be separated from the concepts of at-tawhid (the oneness of Allah) and al-'ubudiyah (servitude to Allah). Tawhid instills the conviction that all human actions are directed solely toward Allah, as stated in His words:

﴿قُلْ إِنَّ صَلَاتِي وَنُسُكِي وَمَحْيَايَ وَمَمَاتِي لِلَّهِ رَبِّ الْعَالَمِينَ (١٦٢)﴾

Meaning: "Say (O Prophet Muhammad), 'Indeed, my prayer, my worship, my life, and my death are solely for Allah, the Lord of all worlds.'" (Qur'an, Surah Al-An'am 6:162).

Meanwhile, 'ubudiyah cultivates an awareness of submission, obedience, and moral conduct in accordance with Allah's commands. Therefore, character education in Islam must be grounded in these two core principles so that it produces individuals who are ṣāliḥun fī nafsihi, muṣliḥun liḡhayriḡ righteous in themselves and a source of goodness for others.³

One of the Qur'anic passages rich in character education values is Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, which contain the counsels of Luqman al-Hakim to his son. These counsels encompass aspects of creed, worship, and social ethics: the prohibition against shirk (associating partners with Allah), the command to show kindness and devotion to one's walidain (parents), awareness of muraqabah Allah (Allah's constant supervision), the obligation to establish prayer, as well as cultivating patience, humility, and gentleness in speech. These verses illustrate that character formation in Islam begins with a proper understanding of tawhid and is manifested through behaviors that reflect submission to Allah and care for others.⁴

In Ibn Kathir's exegesis, it is explained that Luqman's counsel is not merely an ethical admonition, but a manifestation of profound faith. Ibn Kathir interprets Luqman's words, "*Ya bunayya la tusyrik billah*" (O my son, do not associate anything with Allah), as the fundamental basis of character education, indicating that all moral virtues lose their meaning without the foundation of tawhid. From Ibn Kathir's perspective, education emphasizes the inseparable relationship between faith (al-iman), worship (al-'ibadah), and ethics (al-akhlaq). Thus, true character education is a process of tazkiyat al-nafs (purification of the soul) oriented solely toward servitude to Allah.⁵

Based on the explanation above, the research questions in this study are as follows: How is the concept of character education contained in Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, according to Ibn Kathir's exegesis, and how can the approaches of tawhid and 'ubudiyah serve as foundational principles in shaping Islamic character that remains relevant to the context of modern life? This study is expected to enrich the discourse of Islamic education by reaffirming that the success of character education does not lie merely in discipline or social etiquette, but in the formation of a heart that submits to Allah a purified heart that becomes the source of all goodness and noble character.

Research Methods

This study employs a qualitative approach using library research. This approach is chosen because the research focuses on examining classical tafsir texts to explore the values of character education from the perspective of the Qur'an. Library research enables the researcher to thoroughly trace the thoughts of earlier scholars through descriptive-analytical works of exegesis. This method is

² A. M. Fahdini, Y. F. Furnamasari, and D. Anggraeni Dewi, "Urgency of Character Education in Overcoming Moral Crisis Among Students," *Jurnal Penelitian & Teknologi Aplikasi Manajemen (JPTAM)* 5, no. 3 (2021): 9390–9394, accessed November 4, 2025, <https://jptam.org/index.php/jptam/article/download/2485/2162>

³ Taufik Mukmin, "Tawhid and Morality as Core Characters in Islamic Education," *El-Ghiroh: Jurnal Studi Keislaman* 10, no. 1 (2016), accessed November 4, 2025, <https://jurnal.staibslg.ac.id/index.php/el-ghiroh/article/view/50>

⁴ Ahmad Naqib and Darnoto, "Education of Tawhid, Morals, and Worship in the Family: A Study of Surah Luqman 12–19 according to Tafsir Ibn Kathir," *IQRO: Journal of Islamic Education* 8, no. 2 (2024), accessed November 4, 2025, <https://ejournal.iainpalopo.ac.id/index.php/iqro/article/view/8060>

⁵ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi'i, 1994), 400–405.

relevant for uncovering the meaning of character education based on tawhid and ‘ubudiyyah as presented in Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, without conducting fieldwork or collecting empirical data.

The primary data source of this research is Tafsir al-Qur’ān al-‘Azīm by Ibn Kathir (d. 774 H), an authoritative tafsir bil-ma’tsur that is highly relevant for uncovering the authentic meaning of Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, especially concerning tawhid, worship, and ethics. The analysis focuses on a thorough examination of Ibn Kathir’s interpretation to present his conceptual framework in a complete and coherent manner. Secondary data sources include scholarly books, journal articles, and academic works discussing Islamic character education, the values of tawhid, and the concept of ‘ubūdiyyah. These sources serve as supportive references that enrich the interpretation and provide contemporary Islamic context without shifting the central focus from Ibn Kathir’s thought.

Data analysis was carried out using the content analysis method. The analytical steps included: (1) thoroughly reading Ibn Kathir’s tafsir on the selected verses; (2) identifying the character education values that emerge, particularly those related to tawhid and ‘ubudiyyah; (3) categorizing these values into relevant character education themes; and (4) interpreting their relevance to the context of modern education. The final outcome of this analysis is expected to demonstrate that character education in Islam, as illustrated in Ibn Kathir’s exegesis of Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, is fundamentally rooted in the oneness of Allah (at-tawhīd) and total servitude to Him (al-‘ubudiyyah) as the core of noble character formation.

Results and Discussion

An Exegetical Study of Ibn Kathir’s Tafsir on Surah Luqman (Verses 13–19)

﴿ وَإِذْ قَالَ لُقْمَانُ لِابْنِهِ وَهُوَ يَعِظُهُ يَا بُنَيَّ لَا تُشْرِكْ بِاللَّهِ إِنَّ الشِّرْكَ لَظُلْمٌ عَظِيمٌ ۚ ۱۳
 وَوَصَّيْنَا الْإِنْسَانَ بِوَالِدَيْهِ حَمَلَتْهُ أُمُّهُ وَهْنًا عَلَىٰ وَهْنٍ وَفِصَالَهُ فِي سِنَيْنِ ۖ أَنْ إِشْكُرْ لِي وَلِوَالِدَيْكَ إِلَيَّ الْمَصِيرُ ۚ ۱۴
 وَإِنْ جَاهَدَكَ عَلَىٰ أَنْ تُشْرِكَ بِي مَا لَيْسَ لَكَ بِهِ عِلْمٌ فَلَا تُطِعْهُمَا وَصَاحِبُهُمَا فِي الدُّنْيَا مَعْرُوفًا ۖ وَاتَّبِعْ سَبِيلَ مَنْ أَنَابَ إِلَيَّ ثُمَّ إِلَيَّ مَرْجِعُكُمْ فَأُنَبِّئُكُمْ بِمَا كُنْتُمْ تَعْمَلُونَ ۝ ۱۵ ﴾

Meaning: “(Remember) when Luqman said to his son while advising him, ‘O my son, do not associate anything with Allah. Indeed, associating (partners with Him) is truly a great injustice.’” (Qur’an 31:13) “And We have enjoined upon man (to show kindness) to his parents. His mother carried him in weakness upon weakness, and his weaning is in two years. (We said), ‘Be grateful to Me and to your parents; to Me is the final return.’” (Qur’an 31:14) “But if they strive to make you associate with Me that of which you have no knowledge, then do not obey them; yet keep their company in this world with kindness, and follow the path of those who turn to Me. Then to Me will be your return, and I will inform you of what you used to do.” (Qur’an 31:15).⁶

Allah Most High relates the counsel of Luqman to his son, Luqman ibn ‘Unaq ibn Sadun. According to one opinion narrated by As-Suhayli, the name of his son was Tsaran. Allah honored Luqman with the noblest of descriptions and granted him wisdom. Luqman gave this counsel to his son the person he loved most as the greatest form of advice and blessing. He first urged him to worship Allah, the Almighty, who has no partner. Then he warned him, “Indeed, associating partners with Allah is truly a great injustice,” meaning that shirk is the gravest form of wrongdoing.⁷

Al-Bukhari narrates that ‘Abdullah said: “When the verse was revealed, ‘Those who believe and do not mix their faith with wrongdoing (zulm), it is they who will have security, and they are rightly guided’ (Qur’an 6:82), the Companions of the Messenger of Allah ﷺ became distressed. They asked, ‘Which one of us has not mixed his faith with wrongdoing?’ The Messenger of Allah ﷺ replied, ‘That is not what is intended here. Have you not heard the words of Luqman: “O my son, do not associate

⁶ Qur’an, Surah Luqman 31:13–15.

⁷ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 400.

anything with Allah; indeed, associating (partners with Him) is truly a great wrongdoing” (Narrated by Muslim from the hadith of Al-A‘mash).⁸

This hadith clarifies the meaning of Surah Al-An‘am, verse 82, concerning believers who do not mix their faith with wrongdoing. At first, the Companions were anxious because they assumed that ‘wrongdoing’ referred to all types of sin. However, the Prophet ﷺ corrected this understanding by explaining that the ‘wrongdoing’ mentioned in the verse refers specifically to *shirk*, as stated in Surah Luqman, verse 13, which declares that associating partners with Allah is a great injustice. Through this explanation, the Prophet ﷺ affirmed that those who believe in Allah with pure *tawhid*, without mixing it with *shirk*, will attain security from punishment and guidance toward the truth. Sins other than *shirk* do not nullify faith; they only diminish its perfection. This hadith also demonstrates the Prophet’s method of interpreting the Qur’an with the Qur’an, and it emphasizes that true salvation can only be attained by preserving the purity of *tawhid* and avoiding all forms of polytheism.⁹

Allah also says, *“And his weaning is in two years,”* meaning that the mother nurtures and breastfeeds her child for two years after giving birth. This is in accordance with Allah’s statement: *“Mothers shall breastfeed their children for two complete years, for whoever wishes to complete the nursing period.”* (Qur’an 2:233). From this, Ibn ‘Abbas and other leading scholars concluded that the minimum duration of pregnancy is six months, because in another verse Allah says: *“His gestation and his weaning are thirty months.”* (Qur’an 46:15). Allah ﷻ mentions the mother’s nurturing, fatigue, and the difficulty she endures staying awake day and night so that a child may remember the goodness and care his mother has given him. As Allah the Exalted also says: *“And say, ‘My Lord, have mercy upon them both as they raised me when I was small.’”* (Qur’an 17:24).¹⁰

Thus, Allah says: *“Be grateful to Me and to your parents; to Me is your final return.”* This means: I will indeed recompense you with a fitting reward. Then He says: *“But if they strive to make you associate with Me that of which you have no knowledge, do not obey them.”* This means that if your parents exert effort to compel you to follow their religion or to commit *shirk*, you must not obey them. However, this does not exempt you from treating them well in worldly matters in a manner that is *ma‘ruf* showing kindness, respect, and good conduct toward both of them. Allah then says: *“And follow the path of those who turn to Me,”* referring to those who believe. And finally: *“Then to Me will be your return, and I will inform you of what you used to do.”*¹¹

Ath-Thabrani relates in al-‘Asyrah, from Dawud ibn Abi Hind, that Sa‘d ibn Malik said: “This verse was revealed: ‘But if they strive to make you associate with Me that of which you have no knowledge, then do not obey them,’ and so on (*Qur’an 31:15*). I used to be a devoted son to my mother. But when I embraced Islam, my mother said, ‘O Sa‘d, what has happened to you? You will abandon this religion of yours, or I will neither eat nor drink until I die. Then people will call you, “O killer of his own mother.” I replied, ‘Do not do that, Mother, for I will never abandon my religion, no matter what happens!’ She then resolved not to eat for a day and a night, and she was determined in doing so. After that, she continued not eating for another day and night, striving hard to restrain herself. Again, she refrained from eating for a third day and night, persisting in her effort. Seeing my mother grow weaker, I said to her: ‘O Mother, even if you had one hundred souls, and each soul departed one after another, I would not leave this religion of mine. So eat or do not eat as you wish.’ Finally, when my mother saw my determination, she decided to eat.”¹²

The story narrated by Ath-Thabrani illustrates the steadfastness of Sa‘d ibn Malik’s (Sa‘d ibn Abi Waqqas’s) faith and highlights the balance between obedience to Allah and kindness toward one’s

⁸ Ibid., 400.

⁹ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabul Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 401.

¹⁰ Ibid., 401.

¹¹ Ibid., 402.

¹² Ibid., 402.

parents. From this incident, it can be understood that the obligation to honor and serve one's parents must never outweigh the duty to uphold the oneness of Allah and obey Him. When parents command something that contradicts Islamic teachings such as urging a child to commit shirk or abandon the religion their command must not be obeyed. However, even when such a command cannot be followed, the child is still required to treat the parents with kindness, respect, and courtesy in worldly matters.

The story of Sa'd demonstrates an extraordinary example of steadfastness in faith. Despite facing intense emotional pressure from his mother, he remained firm in holding to his belief and refused to abandon Islam. Although he did not comply with his mother's demand, he continued to speak gently and refrained from harming her in any way. His attitude aligns with Allah's command in Surah Luqman, verse 15, which instructs believers not to obey their parents in matters of shirk, yet still to treat them with kindness in worldly affairs. Thus, this narration affirms that obedience to Allah must take precedence over everything else, while doing good to one's parents remains an obligation so long as it does not involve disobedience to Allah.

﴿يُبَيِّنُ لَهَا إِنْ تَكَ مِثْقَالَ حَبَّةٍ مِنْ خَرْدَلٍ فَتَكُنْ فِي صَخْرَةٍ أَوْ فِي السَّمَوَاتِ أَوْ فِي الْأَرْضِ يَأْتِ بِهَا اللَّهُ إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَطِيفٌ خَبِيرٌ ١٦
يُبَيِّنُ لَهَا إِقِمِ الصَّلَاةَ وَأْمُرْ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَانْهَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأَصْبِرْ عَلَىٰ مَا أَصَابَكَ إِنَّ ذَلِكَ مِنْ عَزْمِ الْأُمُورِ ١٧
وَلَا تُصَعِّرْ خَدَّكَ لِلنَّاسِ وَلَا تَمْشِ فِي الْأَرْضِ مَرَحًا إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ كُلَّ مُخْتَالٍ فَخُورٍ ١٨
وَأَقْصِدْ فِي مَشْيِكَ وَاغْضُضْ مِنْ صَوْتِكَ إِنَّ أَنْكَرَ الْأَصْوَاتِ لَصَوْتُ الْحَمِيرِ ١٩﴾

Meaning: (Luqman said,) "O my son, indeed if there is anything [even] the weight of a mustard seed and it is [hidden] within a rock, or in the heavens, or in the earth, Allah will bring it forth. Truly, Allah is Subtle and All-Aware." (Qur'an 31:16) "O my son, establish the prayer, enjoin what is right, and forbid what is wrong, and be patient over whatever befalls you. Indeed, that is among the matters requiring determination." (Qur'an 31:17) "And do not turn your face away from people [in arrogance], nor walk upon the earth with pride. Indeed, Allah does not like every self-deluded and boastful person." (Qur'an 31:18) "And be moderate in your walk, and lower your voice. Indeed, the most disagreeable of sounds is the voice of donkeys." (Qur'an 31:19).¹³

These are the valuable counsels of Luqman al-Hakim that Allah relates so that people may appreciate and emulate them. He said: "O my son, indeed if there is anything even the weight of a mustard seed," referring to wrongdoing or sin no matter how small. The phrase "Allah will bring it forth" indicates that Allah will present every deed on the Day of Judgment when He establishes the scales of justice. Every good deed will be rewarded with goodness, and every evil deed will be repaid with its due punishment. As Allah the Exalted says: "We shall set up the scales of justice on the Day of Resurrection, so no soul will be wronged in the least." (Qur'an 21:47). Even if a mustard seed were hidden within a massive black rock or located in a far, distant place at the edges of the heavens and the earth, Allah would surely bring it forth. Indeed, nothing is hidden from Him, and not even an atom's weight in the heavens or the earth escapes His knowledge.¹⁴

Thus, Allah the Exalted says: "Indeed, Allah is Subtle and All-Aware," indicating the extraordinary subtlety of His knowledge nothing is hidden from Him, no matter how small, fine, or delicate. He knows even the footsteps of an ant in the darkness of a pitch-black night. Then Allah continues: "O my son, establish the prayer," meaning to uphold it with its prescribed limits, fulfill its obligations, and perform it at its appointed times. He then says: "Enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong, and be patient with whatever befalls you," meaning according to your ability and dedication. Be patient with whatever hardship comes your way, for Allah knows that those who carry out *amar*

¹³ Qur'an, Surah Luqman 31:16–19.

¹⁴ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi'i, 1994), 403.

ma'ruf and *nahi munkar* will inevitably face harm or opposition from people. For this reason, He commands patience.¹⁵

Allah then says: “Indeed, that is among the matters requiring determination,” meaning that being patient in the face of harm from people is one of the obligations that must be upheld. Next, His statement: “And do not turn your cheek away from people (in arrogance),” teaches proper conduct in interacting with others. It means: Do not turn your face away from people when speaking to them or when they speak to you, as such behavior suggests disdain or arrogance. Instead, be humble and show a pleasant demeanor toward them.¹⁶

Ibn Jarir explains that the root of the word *tuṣa'ir* (تُصَعِّرُ) is connected to a disease that affects camels, particularly in the hump and head, causing the hump to bend toward the head. This physical condition was then used metaphorically to describe arrogance in humans. An example of this usage appears in the words of ‘Amr ibn Hayy al-Taghlibi: “In the past, when arrogant people bent their faces away, we would straighten their tilt until they stood upright again.”¹⁷

Allah the Almighty says: “And do not walk upon the earth with arrogance,” meaning with pride, haughtiness, authoritarian behavior, or conceit. Do not act in such a manner, for if you do so, Allah will certainly be displeased with you. For this reason, He says: “Indeed, Allah does not like every self-deluded and boastful person,” meaning one who is arrogant and proud of himself, and *fakhr* one who is boastful toward others. Then Allah says: “And be moderate in your walk,” instructing us to walk in a balanced manner not excessively slow nor overly fast, but with dignity and moderation. His statement: “And lower your voice,” implies that one should not be excessive in speech nor raise the voice unnecessarily in matters that bring no benefit. Hence, He says: “Indeed, the most unpleasant of sounds is the voice of donkeys.”¹⁸

Mujahid and many scholars of tafsir said: “Indeed, the worst of voices is the voice of donkeys,” referring to a sound that is excessively loud and harsh—likened to that of a donkey in its intensity and coarseness. Such a voice is detested in the sight of Allah ﷻ. The comparison to a donkey highlights the inherently blameworthy and reprehensible nature of such behavior. This is further supported by the saying of the Messenger of Allah ﷺ:

لَيْسَ لَنَا مَثَلُ السَّوِّءِ الْعَائِدِ فِي هَبْتِهِ كَالْكَلْبِ يَعُودُ فِي قَيْبِهِ

Meaning: “He is not one of us. The worst of examples is the one who takes back his gift like a dog that vomits and then returns to eat its own vomit.” (*Muttafaq ‘alayh*)

An-Nasa’i, in his commentary on this verse, narrates a hadith from Abu Hurayrah (may Allah be pleased with him) in which the Prophet ﷺ said:

إِذَا سَمِعْتُمْ صِيَاخَ الدِّيَكَةِ فَاسْأَلُوا اللَّهَ مِنْ فَضْلِهِ فَإِنَّهَا رَأَتْ مَلَكًا وَإِذَا سَمِعْتُمْ نَهيقَ الحِمَارِ فَتَعَوَّدُوا بِاللَّهِ مِنَ الشَّيْطَانِ فَإِنَّهُ رَأَى شَيْطَانًا

Meaning: “When you hear the crowing of a rooster, ask Allah for His bounty, for it has seen an angel. And when you hear the braying of a donkey, seek refuge in Allah from Satan, for it has seen a devil.” (This hadith is also narrated by several collectors other than Ibn Majah. In some versions, the phrase “at night” is added. And Allah knows best.)¹⁹

These are the beneficial counsels and the noble Qur’anic narratives concerning Luqman al-Hakim. Many pieces of wisdom and advice have been transmitted from him. Imam Ahmad narrates from Ibn ‘Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) that the Messenger of Allah ﷺ said:

إِنَّ لِقْمَانَ الْحَكِيمِ كَانَ يَقُولُ إِنَّ اللَّهَ إِذَا اسْتُودِعَ شَيْئًا حَفِظَهُ

¹⁵ Ibid.,403.

¹⁶ Ibid.,403.

¹⁷ Ibid.,403.

¹⁸ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 404.

¹⁹ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 405.

Meaning: “Indeed, Luqman al-Hakim said: ‘When Allah entrusts something to someone, He surely protects it.’”²⁰

The Concept and Essence of Character Education in Islam

Character education is a fundamental aspect in shaping a whole and well-rounded human personality morally, spiritually, and socially. In the modern context, Thomas Lickona defines character education as a deliberate effort to cultivate virtues such as honesty, responsibility, and compassion for others through the habituation of moral values in daily life.²¹ In Indonesia, the Ministry of Education and Culture also emphasizes that character education aims to shape individuals who are faithful, pious, noble in character, independent, and responsible in their roles as members of the nation and society.²² Thus, character education is not merely the transfer of moral knowledge, but the formation of a personality grounded in spiritual values and universal ethical principles.

Character is closely associated with personality or morality (*akhlaq*). Personality refers to the distinctive traits or characteristics a person possesses, shaped by environmental influences such as family during childhood as well as innate factors from birth. In line with this understanding, some hold the view that a person’s character, whether good or bad, is already inherent from birth. If someone is born with a virtuous soul, they will naturally develop good character; conversely, if one’s soul is corrupt, they will incline toward bad character. If this view were accurate, character education would be futile, since it would be impossible to change a character considered permanent. However, another group argues the opposite: that character can indeed be shaped and developed. Therefore, character education becomes essential in guiding individuals toward the development of good character.²³

In the Islamic perspective, character education is known as *tarbiyah al-akhlaq* (moral cultivation) or *tahdhib al-akhlaq* (moral refinement), which refers to the effort to improve and purify one’s character so that it aligns with the values taught by Allah SWT. Al-Ghazali, in *Ihya’ ‘Ulum ad-Din*, emphasizes: “The purpose of education is the purification of the soul and the cultivation of proper conduct; the purer a person’s soul becomes, the better their character will be.”²⁴

This concept affirms that the essence of character education in Islam is *tazkiyah an-nafs* (purification of the soul) and *ta’dib* (the formation of proper conduct). These two elements give rise to moral awareness rooted in a person’s relationship with Allah (*ḥablun min Allah*) and with fellow human beings (*ḥablun min an-nas*). Therefore, character education in Islam does not stop at mastering social ethical values; rather, it demands *ihsan* the moral and spiritual excellence of doing good with full awareness of Allah’s constant watchfulness, as the Prophet ﷺ said: “Ihsan is that you worship Allah as if you see Him; and if you cannot see Him, then indeed He sees you.” (Narrated by Muslim).²⁵

Azyumardi Azra explains that the primary goals of Islamic education encompass three dimensions: *tawḥid al-‘aqidah* (the cultivation of faith), *sihhat al-‘ibadah* (the establishment of correct worship), and *kamal al-akhlaq* (the perfection of moral character).²⁶ These three dimensions form an integrated and comprehensive (*shamil*) system of character education. Within this framework, *at-tawḥid* serves as the moral foundation that orients one’s life solely toward Allah, while *al-‘ubudiyah* becomes the path for actualizing these values through obedience, worship, and refined social conduct. Thus,

²⁰ Ibid., 405.

²¹ Thomas Lickona, *Educating for Character: How Our Schools Can Teach Respect and Responsibility* (New York: Bantam Books, 1991), 53.

²² Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia, *Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter (PPK): Konsep dan Implementasi* (Jakarta: Kemdikbud, 2017), 12.

²³ Dahrun Sajadi, “Character Education in the Islamic Perspective,” *Tahdzib Al-Akhlaq: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 2, no. 2 (2019), Universitas Islam As-Syafi’iyah, accessed November 4, 2025, <https://www.jurnal.uia.ac.id/index.php/Tahdzib/article/view/510>.

²⁴ Al-Ghazali, *Ihya’ ‘Ulum al-Din*, vol. 3 (Jeddah: Dar al-Minhaj, 2023), 56.

²⁵ Ibid., 57.

²⁶ Azyumardi Azra, *Pendidikan Islam: Tradisi dan Modernisasi di Tengah Tantangan Milenium III* (Jakarta: Kencana, 2012), 88.

Islamic character education aims to shape individuals who are *ṣāliḥ li nafsih, nafi' li ghayrih* (righteous for themselves and beneficial to others).²⁷

From the perspective of Qur'anic exegesis, Ibn Kathir views true moral education as beginning with the cultivation of *tawhid* and manifested through proper worship. In *Tafsir al-Qur'an al-'Azim*, he frequently emphasizes the close relationship between *al-iman*, *al-'ibadah*, and *al-akhlāq* (faith, worship, and ethics) as the pillars of human character formation. In his interpretation of Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, Ibn Kathir explains that all of Luqman's counsel to his son represents a process of *ta'dib rabbani* (divine moral education) that instills *tawhid*, guides correct worship, and shapes social conduct. Thus, the essence of character education according to Ibn Kathir is an integrative process that nurtures faith, regulates behavior, and produces social righteousness based on a deep awareness of servitude to Allah SWT. As He says: “*Truly successful is the one who purifies it (the soul), and truly ruined is the one who corrupts it.*” (*Qur'an, Surah Ash-Shams 91:9–10*).

Character Education through the Tawhid-Based Approach

Tawhid comes from the phrase *wahḥada-yuwahḥidu-tawḥidan*, which means “to unify” or “to make one.” In this context, *tawhid* refers to the concept of affirming the oneness of Allah SWT in all His names, attributes, divinity (*uluhiyyah*), and lordship (*rububiyyah*). The concept of monotheism emphasizes the belief that there is only one God Allah and that no other deity exists besides Him. It affirms that Allah has no partners in creation or in sustaining life. Allah alone is the Creator, the Provider, and the Lord (*Rabb*) who governs the entire universe. *Tawhid* also asserts that none of Allah's exalted names or attributes can be equaled or compared to Him.²⁸

The concept of *at-tawhid* or monotheism is the core of all Islamic teachings and serves as the primary foundation of character education. Without the grounding of *tawhid*, education would produce nothing more than rational intelligence devoid of spiritual values. In this context, Ibn Kathir's commentary on Surah Luqman, verse 13, presents the most fundamental depiction of *tawhid*-based character education. Allah says:

{ وَإِذْ قَالَ لُقْمَانُ لِابْنِهِ وَهُوَ يَعِظُهُ يَا بُنَيَّ لَا تُشْرِكْ بِاللَّهِ إِنَّ الشِّرْكَ لَظُلْمٌ عَظِيمٌ ۝ ١٣ }

Meaning: “(Remember) when Luqman said to his son while advising him, ‘O my son, do not associate anything with Allah. Indeed, associating (partners with Him) is truly a great wrongdoing.’” (*Qur'an, Surah Luqman 31:13*).

In his exegesis, Ibn Kathir explains that the phrase “*al-zulmu al-'azim*” refers to *shirk billah* associating partners with Allah in worship. He cites the statement of the Companion ‘Abdullah ibn Mas‘ud, who related that when Surah Al-An‘ām (6:82) was revealed, the Companions asked the Messenger of Allah ﷺ about the meaning of “wrongdoing.” The Prophet ﷺ replied: “It is not as you think; indeed, the wrongdoing mentioned here is *shirk*. Have you not heard Luqman's words to his son: ‘Indeed, *shirk* is a great wrongdoing?’”²⁹ This passage shows that the very first form of education Luqman gave to his son was education in creed (*'aqidah*), not social morality or practical ethics. Ibn Kathir interprets this to mean that *tawhid* is the primary foundation of all deeds and the true source of moral values, for: “Whoever does not affirm the oneness of Allah, his natural disposition (*fitrah*) becomes corrupted and his path becomes misguided.”

In the context of character education, *tawhid* teaches humans to recognize their position as servants of Allah (*'abd Allah*) and as His vicegerents on earth (*khalifah fi al-ard*). This awareness cultivates the values of honesty (*ṣidq*), responsibility (*amanah*), and moral courage (*shaja'ah*), because every human action will be held accountable before Allah SWT. These values are aligned with the

²⁷ Samsul Nizar, *Filsafat Pendidikan Islam: Pendekatan Historis, Teoritis, dan Praktis* (Jakarta: Ciputat Press, 2002), 110.

²⁸ A. Arifah, S. F. Sinaga, and R. Pasaribu, “Tawhid and Morality as Core Characters in Islamic Education,” *Integrasi: Jurnal Studi Islam dan Humaniora* 2, no. 1 (2024): 43–57, accessed November 4, 2025, <https://www.ejurnalilmiah.com/index.php/integrasi/article/view/11328>

²⁹ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabul Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi'i, 1994), 400.

purpose of Islamic education as explained by al-Ghazali, namely to form individuals who “*prepare themselves to know Allah and to worship Him.*”³⁰

In addition, tawhid instills the awareness of *muraqabah* (the conviction that Allah constantly observes all actions). This is reflected in Allah’s words in Surah Luqman, verse 16, which state:

﴿ يٰبُنَيَّ اِنَّهَا اِنْ تَكَ مِثْقَالَ حَبَّةٍ مِنْ خَرْدَلٍ فَتَكُنْ فِيْ صَخْرَةٍ اَوْ فِي السَّمٰوٰتِ اَوْ فِي الْاَرْضِ يٰٓاْتِ بِهَا اللّٰهُ اِنَّ اللّٰهَ لَطِيْفٌ خَبِيْرٌ ۙ ۱۶ ﴾

Meaning: “(Luqman said,) ‘O my son, indeed if there is anything—even the weight of a mustard seed and it is hidden within a rock, or in the heavens, or in the earth, Allah will bring it forth. Truly, Allah is Subtle and All-Aware.’” (Qur’an 31:16).

This value is crucial in shaping a student’s internal character, as it cultivates intrinsic motivation to do good without needing to be monitored by others. Within the framework of Islamic education, *muraqabah* serves as the foundation for developing honesty and a strong sense of responsibility.

Ibn Kathir also interprets verse 16 as conveying that Allah will recompense every deed whether good or evil even if it is as small as a mustard seed. This will be made manifest on the Day of Judgment. Nothing is hidden from Allah; He knows everything, both the visible and the unseen. This verse also reflects the intelligence and awareness required to recognize the existence of the Creator and to understand that Allah has complete knowledge of all things, whether apparent or concealed. Allah continuously watches over His servants in every circumstance and at every moment.³¹

Providing motivation, encouragement, and emotional support are essential components in teaching tawhid and instilling the awareness that Allah continuously watches over these children. It is not sufficient merely to explain the concept of tawhid theoretically; rather, students must internalize it deeply. This is illustrated by Luqman al-Hakim when he advised his son. He began his counsel with the phrase “*ya bunayya*” (“my dear son”), reflecting profound affection in delivering religious instruction. From this perspective, the role of faith is to transform a person’s behavior. A true believer will develop noble character, engage in righteous deeds that contribute to society, and promote peace. With firm conviction, Muslims who nurture strong faith will be more resilient in facing external temptations that may lead to harmful actions.

Thus, the tawhid-based approach to character education according to Ibn Kathir does not merely function as the formation of theological belief, but also as the foundation of moral and spiritual consciousness. Tawhid produces a God-centered character one oriented toward Allah fostering integrity, responsibility, and consistency in action. Education grounded in tawhid shapes individuals who speak the truth, act justly, and remain uninfluenced by worldly interests, because all of their deeds are guided by the words of Allah SWT:

﴿ قُلْ اِنَّ صَلَاتِيْ وَنُسُكِيْ وَمَحْيَايَ وَمَمَاتِيْ لِلّٰهِ رَبِّ الْعٰلَمِيْنَ ۙ ۱۶۲ ﴾

Meaning: “Say (O Prophet Muhammad), ‘Indeed, my prayer, my worship, my life, and my death are solely for Allah, the Lord of all worlds.’” (Qur’an, Surah Al-An’am 6:162).³²

Thus, character education through a tawhid-based approach in Ibn Kathir’s interpretation can be understood as a process of *tawhid al-fiṭrah bi al-wahy* (the harmonization of human innate disposition with divine revelation) is returning the human being to his original consciousness as a believer who submits to Allah SWT. Tawhid not only rectifies one’s belief but also shapes a personality that is honest, steadfast, and oriented toward divine truth. In this way, tawhid becomes the spiritual foundation for forming an authentic and resilient Islamic character amid the moral challenges of the modern age.

³⁰ Al-Ghozali, *Ihya’ Ulūm al-Dīn*, Vol 3 (Jeddah: Dar Al-Minhaj, 2023), 12.

³¹ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabul Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 403.

³² Taufik Mukmin, “Tawhid and Morality as Core Characters in Islamic Education,” *El-Ghiroh: Jurnal Studi Keislaman* 10, no. 1 (2016), accessed November 4, 2025, <https://jurnal.staibslg.ac.id/index.php/el-ghiroh/article/view/50>

Character Education through the ‘Ubudiyyah-Based Approach

Linguistically, *‘ubudiyyah* refers to an attitude of devotion and humility, expressing submission and a sense of weakness before the Creator. In general, *‘ubudiyyah* denotes worship that is, carrying out Allah’s commands in daily life while fulfilling one’s responsibilities as His servant. Given its significance, *‘ubudiyyah* deserves serious attention and guidance, both in formal and informal education. This is because, in society and ultimately in the Hereafter, human beings who are blessed with intellect naturally strive to attain a meaningful and prosperous life.³³

In today’s modern era, there has been a noticeable decline in religious values and a weakening awareness of worship practices, especially among teenagers. Yet religious consciousness particularly in the realm of *‘ubudiyyah* is an essential quality that every adolescent must possess. The erosion of these values and this awareness is largely due to inadequate religious education, negative environmental influences, and the rapid advancement of modern times, which unfortunately often brings harmful effects. Adolescence is a critical stage in human development, marked by the search for identity and the formation of moral and spiritual values. During this phase, young people strive to understand who they are, what their purpose is, and which values they wish to adopt as guiding principles in life. However, in this process of exploration, adolescents often experience confusion and inconsistency in fulfilling their religious obligations. At times they appear diligent in worship, yet at other times they become neglectful or reluctant to perform it.

This fluctuation in worship observance reflects the psychological dynamics and the incompletely formed character of adolescents. Teenagers are often influenced by internal factors such as emotions and motivation as well as external factors, including social environments, social media, and modern cultural trends that frequently shift attention away from spiritual values. In this context, character education plays a strategic role in shaping adolescents into individuals who possess strong values, integrity, and discipline in practicing their religious teachings. Allah commands His servants to worship Him, for the very essence of a servant is devotion to his Lord. Allah the Almighty says:

{ وَمَا خَلَقْتُ الْجِنَّ وَالْإِنْسَ إِلَّا لِيَعْبُدُونِ ٥٦ }

Meaning: “I did not create jinn and humans except to worship Me.” (*Qur’an, Surah Adh-Dhariyat 51:56*).³⁴

Therefore, character education based on the approach of *‘ubūdiyyah* is crucial in shaping a generation that is faithful, ethical, and noble in character. This approach emphasizes the integration of spiritual strengthening and moral formation through the conscious and consistent practice of worship. Through *‘ubudiyyah*-based character education, learners not only understand religious teachings cognitively but also internalize them affectively and practically as an expression of servitude to Allah SWT.

Imam al-Ghazali, in *Ihya’ ‘Ulum al-Din*, explains that every act of worship possesses an inner secret (*asrar al-‘ibadah*) aimed at purifying the soul and cultivating noble character. In prayer (*salah*), its inner secret lies in the presence of the heart and understanding the meaning of its recitations, which train discipline, honesty, and inner tranquility. Fasting embodies the values of self-control, patience, empathy, and sincerity in restraining the desires of the soul. As for zakat, it is not merely a financial obligation but also a means of purifying the heart from miserliness and attachment to worldly possessions, while fostering social concern, generosity, and gratitude to Allah.³⁵ Meanwhile, according to al-Ghazali, the pilgrimage (*hajj*) is a spiritual journey toward Allah that trains humility, patience, and the unity of the Muslim community. Each rite carries a profound spiritual meaning such as *ihram*, which

³³Mohammad Nur Hassan and Imron Fauzi, “Coaching ‘Ubudiyyah in Junior High School Muhammadiyah 1 Genteng,” *Adabiyah: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 2, no. 1 (2024): 52, accessed November 5, 2025, <https://aladabiyah.uinkhas.ac.id/index.php/adabiyah/article/download/28/41>.

³⁴ Ibid., 53.

³⁵ Al-Ghozali, *Ihya’ ‘Ulūm al-Dīn*, Vol 1 (Jeddah: Dar Al-Minhaj, 2023), 418-589.

symbolizes the purity of intention, and the stoning of the *jumrah*, which symbolizes the struggle against one's carnal desires. Overall, the inner dimensions of worship highlighted by al-Ghazali emphasize *tazkiyat al-nafs* (purification of the soul) as the core of Islamic character education. Thus, worship is not merely an outward ritual, but a means of moral and spiritual formation, shaping individuals to possess noble character and a fully developed personality.³⁶

Worship (*ibadah*) plays a highly significant role in shaping a person's character. Essentially, worship is not merely understood as a set of ritual activities such as prayer, fasting, almsgiving, and pilgrimage but also as a process of internalizing spiritual values that form one's personality and behavior. Through worship, individuals are trained to be disciplined, honest, patient, and submissive to divine commandments all of which are essential components for developing strong and noble character. The influence of worship on character is evident in the way it instills moral and spiritual values into daily life. Prayer, for instance, teaches punctuality and submission to Allah; fasting cultivates patience and self-control; zakat nurtures social concern; and hajj instills a sense of equality and sincerity. Collectively, these acts of worship are designed to train individuals to develop good character, for true worship is ultimately reflected in positive behavior and sound social relationships.³⁷

If a person performs worship correctly, the character that develops will reflect noble Islamic values. Conversely, worship performed without sincerity, reflection, or accompanying behavioral change becomes nothing more than a formal routine devoid of meaning. Therefore, the quality of one's worship is directly proportional to the quality of one's character. The more sincere and excellent a person's worship is, the more virtuous the character they will display in real life.³⁸ Thus, worship serves not only as a means of drawing closer to Allah SWT but also as an effective instrument of character education. Through worship, individuals are guided to develop a balanced relationship between their spiritual, moral, and social dimensions, thereby shaping a person who is faithful, possesses integrity, and embodies noble character (*akhlaq karimah*).

Allah SWT has stated in Surah Luqman, where Luqman advises his son to show kindness to his parents (*birr al-walidayn*), as follows:

﴿ وَوَصَّيْنَا الْإِنْسَانَ بِوَالِدَيْهِ حَمَلَتْهُ أُمُّهُ وَهْنًا عَلَى وَهْنٍ وَفِصَالَهُ فِي عَامَيْنِ أَنْ اشْكُرْ لِي وَلِوَالِدَيْكَ إِلَيَّ الْمَصِيرُ ١٤ وَإِنْ جَاهَدَكَ عَلَى أَنْ تُشْرِكَ بِي مَا لَيْسَ لَكَ بِهِ عِلْمٌ فَلَا تُطِعْهُمَا وَصَاحِبْهُمَا فِي الدُّنْيَا مَعْرُوفًا وَاتَّبِعْ سَبِيلَ مَنْ أَنَابَ إِلَيَّ ثُمَّ إِلَيَّ مَرْجِعُكُمْ فَأُنَبِّئُكُمْ بِمَا كُنْتُمْ تَعْمَلُونَ ﴿ ١٥ ﴾

Meaning: "And We have enjoined upon man (to be good) to his parents. His mother carried him in weakness upon weakness, and his weaning is in two years. (We said), 'Be grateful to Me and to your parents; to Me is the final return.' (Qur'an 31:14) "But if they strive to make you associate with Me that of which you have no knowledge, then do not obey them; yet accompany them in this world with kindness, and follow the path of those who turn to Me. Then to Me will be your return, and I will inform you of what you used to do." (Qur'an 31:15)

The verses above illustrate the principle of balance in *'ubudiyah* that servitude to Allah does not negate honoring one's parents, and honoring one's parents must never contradict the principles of tawhid. Values such as *shukr* (gratitude), *hilm* (forbearance and gentleness), and *ta'zim* (respect and reverence) are integral aspects of character education that emerge from a deep awareness of *'ubudiyah*.

Ibn Kathir also explains that the command to show kindness to one's parents (*birr al-walidayn*) comes immediately after the command to affirm Allah's oneness, as a form of *talazum bayna al-'ibadah wa al-ta'ah* "the inseparable link between worshipping Allah and obeying one's parents." He emphasizes that gratitude to Allah and to one's parents is part of true servitude, as expressed in the

³⁶ Ibid., 589-645.

³⁷ Abdul Rohim, Ali Iskandar Zulkarnain, and Aghnaita, "Development of Students' Social Behavior: An Analysis of the Influence of Worship Obedience in Learning," *Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam Al-Thariqah* 9, no. 1 (January–June 2024), accessed November 5, 2025, [https://doi.org/10.25299/al-thariqah.2024.vol9\(1\).16593](https://doi.org/10.25299/al-thariqah.2024.vol9(1).16593)

³⁸ Imam Suprayogo, "Ikhlās: The Most Essential Part of Worship," UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, October 13, 2015, accessed November 5, 2025, <https://uin-malang.ac.id/r/151001/ikhlas-bagian-terpenting-dari-ibadah.html>.

verse: “Be grateful to Me and to your parents.”³⁹ However, when obedience to parents conflicts with the commands of Allah, the priority must remain with the Creator. Ibn Kathir cites the hadith of the Prophet ﷺ:

لا طاعة لمخلوق في معصية الخالق

Meaning: “There is no obedience to any created being when it involves disobedience to the Creator.” (Narrated by Ahmad).

Allah SWT states in Surah Luqman, where Luqman advises his son to establish prayer and uphold the call to *amar ma'ruf nahi munkar*, as follows:

﴿يُنَبِّئُ أَقِمِ الصَّلَاةَ وَأْمُرْ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَانْهَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأَصْبِرْ عَلَىٰ مَا أَصَابَكَ إِنَّ ذَٰلِكَ مِنْ عَزْمِ الْأُمُورِ ١٧﴾

Meaning: “O my son, establish the prayer, enjoin what is right, and forbid what is wrong, and be patient over whatever befalls you. Indeed, that is among the matters requiring determination.” (Qur'an 31:17)

The verse above shows a very strong connection between acts of worship specifically prayer and the mission of *amar ma'ruf nahi munkar*, along with patience in facing trials and difficulties. Patience itself is one of the fundamental character traits that every servant of Allah must possess. Another Qur'anic verse that demonstrates the close relationship between worship and moral character is Allah's statement: “Indeed, prayer restrains from indecency and wrongdoing.” (Qur'an 29:45). This means that worship particularly prayer should have a positive impact on one's daily behavior and character.⁴⁰

Worship has a significant impact on social life. Proper worship not only strengthens one's relationship with Allah SWT, but also enhances relationships among people. Values such as honesty, justice, and empathy become the foundation for creating a harmonious society. A Muslim who worships with full awareness will uphold honesty and show respect toward others. Thus, the concept of *'ubudiyah* encompasses the development of moral and social character that reflects obedience to Allah and compassion toward fellow human beings.⁴¹

The Qur'an affirms the connection between worship and social conduct in its words in Surah Luqman, verses 18–19:

﴿وَلَا تَصَعِّرْ خَدَّكَ لِلنَّاسِ وَلَا تَمْشِ فِي الْأَرْضِ مَرَحًا إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ كُلَّ مُخْتَالٍ فَخُورٍ ١٨ وَأَقْصِدْ فِي مَشْيِكَ وَاغْضُضْ مِنْ صَوْتِكَ إِنَّ أَنْكَرَ الْأَصْوَاتِ لَصَوْتُ الْحَمِيرِ ١٩﴾

Meaning: “And do not turn your face away from people [in arrogance], nor walk upon the earth with pride. Indeed, Allah does not like every self-deluded and boastful person.” (Qur'an 31:18)
“And be moderate in your walk, and lower your voice. Indeed, the most disagreeable of sounds is the voice of donkeys.” (Qur'an 31:19).

According to Ibn Jarir al-Ṭabari, the expression “*wa la tuṣa'ir khaddaka li-n-nas*” (“and do not turn your face away from people”) in Surah Luqman verse 18 originates from *ash-shu'ar*, a disease in camels that causes the neck to bend to one side. This metaphor illustrates an attitude of arrogance and disdain toward others. Al-Ṭabari emphasizes that Allah forbids arrogance because it corrupts social relationships and contradicts the essence of *'ubudiyah*, which requires humility and mutual respect. Ibn Kathir, in interpreting the verse “*wa-ghdud min sawtik*” (“and lower your voice”), explains that Allah commands people to speak gently and not to raise their voices unnecessarily. His statement “*inna*

³⁹ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi'i, 1994), 402.

⁴⁰ Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi'i, 1994), 404.

⁴¹ Abdul Munir and Syukurman, “The Impact of Islamic Values on Moral Development and Pro-Social Behavior among Sociology Education Students at STKIP Bima,” *Edu Sociata: Jurnal Pendidikan Sosiologi*, STKIP Bima, accessed November 5, 2025, <https://jurnal.stkipbima.ac.id/index.php/ES/article/view/1127/654>.

ankara al-aṣwat lasawtu al-hamir” (“indeed, the most unpleasant of sounds is the voice of donkeys”) serves as a metaphor for harsh and useless speech.⁴²

Thus, genuine worship should be reflected in a character that is courteous, humble, and refined. A servant who truly understands the essence of *‘ubūdiyyah* naturally strives to embody noble qualities. Such a person demonstrates honesty, modesty, and gentle speech in all interactions. These virtues arise from a heart shaped by sincere devotion and awareness of Allah. Ultimately, they serve as a mirror of the depth of one’s worship and the strength of one’s faith.

Conclusion

The exegesis of Ibn Kathir on Surah Luqman, verses 13–19, affirms that Islamic character education cannot be separated from its two fundamental pillars: tawhid and moral ethics. Through the counsel of Luqman al-Hakim to his son, the Qur’an conveys essential messages such as preserving the purity of faith by avoiding shirk, honoring one’s parents, and cultivating gratitude. Tawhid serves as the foundation for building strong character, nurturing a sense of responsibility, and guiding individuals toward choosing the right path in life. From the perspective of moral ethics, Luqman’s advice highlights the importance of worship particularly prayer enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong, patience, humility, and refined speech. Good moral conduct is viewed as the fruit of proper worship and an indicator of the quality of one’s social relationships. Moral ethics also play a crucial role in strengthening social order by fostering honesty, humility, and mutual respect within the community.

Thus, Ibn Kathir’s interpretation of Surah Luqman offers a significant contribution to Islamic character education by shaping individuals who possess strong faith, noble character, devotion to their parents, humility in social interactions, and a deep sense of responsibility before Allah and fellow human beings. These values remain highly relevant as foundational principles for developing Islamic education capable of addressing contemporary moral challenges.

References

- Al-Ghazali. *Ihya’ ‘Ulum al-Din*. Vols. I and III. Jeddah: Dar Al-Minhaj, 2023.
- Al-Sheikh, Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq. *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*. Translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari. Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994.
- Amrillah, Mafaza, and Ainun Nadlif. “Pendidikan Karakter Anak Usia Dini pada Surah Luqman Ayat 12–19 Berdasarkan Tafsir Ibnu Katsir.” *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi* 23, no. 3 (October 2023): 2570–2577. <https://doi.org/10.33087/jiubj.v23i3.4222>.
- Arifah, A., S. F. Sinaga, and R. Pasaribu. “Tauhid dan Moral sebagai Karakter Utama dalam Pendidikan Islam.” *Integrasi: Jurnal Studi Islam dan Humaniora* 2, no. 1 (2024): 43–57. Accessed November 4, 2025. <https://www.ejurnalilmiah.com/index.php/integrasi/article/view/11328>.
- Azra, Azyumardi. *Pendidikan Islam: Tradisi dan Modernisasi di Tengah Tantangan Milenium III*. Jakarta: Kencana, 2012.
- Dahrin Sajadi. “Pendidikan Karakter dalam Perspektif Islam.” *Tahdzib Al-Akhlak: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 2, no. 2 (2019). Universitas Islam As-Syafi’iyah. Accessed November 4, 2025. <https://www.jurnal.uia.ac.id/index.php/Tahdzib/article/view/510>.
- Fahdini, A. M., Y. F. Furnamasari, and D. Anggraeni Dewi. “Urgensi Pendidikan Karakter dalam Mengatasi Krisis Moral di Kalangan Siswa.” *Jurnal Penelitian & Teknologi Aplikasi Manajemen (JPTAM)* 5, no. 3 (2021): 9390–9394. Accessed November 4, 2025. <https://jptam.org/index.php/jptam/article/download/2485/2162>.
- Hassan, Mohammad Nur, and Imron Fauzi. “Coaching ‘Ubudiyah in Junior High School Muhammadiyah 1 Genteng.” *Adabiyah: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 2, no. 1 (2024): 52–53.

⁴²Abdullah bin Muhammad bin Abdurrahman bin Ishaq Al-Sheikh, *Lubaabut Tafsir min Ibni Katsir*, translated by M. Abdul Ghoffar E. M. and Abu Ihsan al-Atsari (Bogor: Pustaka Imam asy-Syafi’i, 1994), 405.

- Accessed November 5, 2025. <https://aladabiyah.uinkhas.ac.id/index.php/adabiyah/article/download/28/41>.
- Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia. *Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter (PPK): Konsep dan Implementasi*. Jakarta: Kemdikbud, 2017.
- Lickona, Thomas. *Educating for Character: How Our Schools Can Teach Respect and Responsibility*. New York: Bantam Books, 1991.
- Mukmin, Taufik. "Tauhid dan Moral sebagai Karakter Utama dalam Pendidikan Islam." *El-Ghiroh: Jurnal Studi Keislaman* 10, no. 1 (2016). Accessed November 4, 2025. <https://jurnal.staibslg.ac.id/index.php/el-ghiroh/article/view/50>.
- Munir, Abdul, and Syukurman. "Dampak Nilai-Nilai Islam pada Perkembangan Moral dan Perilaku Pro-Sosial pada Mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Sosiologi STKIP Bima." *Edu Sociata: Jurnal Pendidikan Sosiologi*. STKIP Bima. Accessed November 5, 2025. <https://jurnal.stkipbima.ac.id/index.php/ES/article/view/1127/654>.
- Naqib, Ahmad, and Darnoto. "Pendidikan Tauhid, Akhlak, dan Ibadah dalam Keluarga: Kajian Surah Luqman 12–19 menurut Tafsir Ibnu Katsir." *IQRO: Journal of Islamic Education* 8, no. 2 (2024). Accessed November 4, 2025. <https://ejournal.iainpalopo.ac.id/index.php/iqro/article/view/8060>.
- Nizar, Samsul. *Filsafat Pendidikan Islam: Pendekatan Historis, Teoritis, dan Praktis*. Jakarta: Ciputat Press, 2002.
- Rohim, Abdul, Ali Iskandar Zulkarnain, and Aghnaita. "Pengembangan Perilaku Sosial Santri Madrasah: Analisis Pengaruh Ketaatan Ibadah dalam Pembelajaran." *Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam Al-Thariqah* 9, no. 1 (January–June 2024). Accessed November 5, 2025. [https://doi.org/10.25299/al-thariqah.2024.vol9\(1\).16593](https://doi.org/10.25299/al-thariqah.2024.vol9(1).16593).
- Suprayogo, Imam. "Ikhlas Bagian Terpenting dari Ibadah." UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, October 13, 2015. Accessed November 5, 2025. <https://uin-malang.ac.id/r/151001/ikhlas-bagian-terpenting-dari-ibadah.html>.